

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING MILITARY TERMS IN ENGLISH

Darvishova Gulchehra Kenjabayevna

The University of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13751459>

Annotation. Mastering common military words is a great way to improve your vocabulary related to the armed services. In this work, we present ideas about the significance of using military terms in English and its importance in the understanding of contexts and specialized texts.

Key words: term, importance, context, comprehend, concepts, linguistic world, commands, content.

We need to be very careful with selecting and presenting the content paying special attention to the military terminology our students need.

Using military terms plays an important role in the understanding of contexts and specialized texts. Understanding the intricate terminological details of the technical and scientific contexts helps students comprehend what the main message of the document is, and it helps specialists to transmit the content more effectively.

The U.S. military uses many unique items and concepts that civilians aren't exposed to. Because of this and the need for expedient, clear communication, service members are immersed in a linguistic world apart from the daily life of a civilian. Military education is valuable because it provides an intellectual architecture for battlefield success. It contributes to stable civil-military relations, a culture of reflection, and a capacity for critical analysis.

Those serving in the military use their own terminology to communicate with each other. This helps them quickly transfer important messages back and forth. Awareness of basic military terms can help you better understand the rules and terminology you'll receive if you onboard with a U.S. military base. Military terms and why they may be important to know if you pursue a position in the military.

Members serving in the U.S. Air Force, Army, Navy, Marines, and Coast Guard use military terms recognizable throughout all sections of the military. Some of this terminology may be known only to members within their respective branches. Others can be more basic and related to all military branches. Military language can communicate an attack, a specific meeting location or drill commands.

Mastering common military words is a great way to improve your vocabulary related to the armed services. To become even more fluent in military terminology, review a list of military acronyms, take a deep dive into some military slang sayings, or explore how to write the date in military format. The Military Has a Vocabulary all its own. The U.S. military uses many unique items and concepts that civilians aren't exposed to. Because of this and the need for expedient, clear communication, service members are immersed in a linguistic world apart from the daily life of a civilian. Some are self-explanatory and others are completely cryptic, but they each have a specific and important (sometimes) meaning. Here are a few common military terms members may use regularly:

A - Air Picket -- Any airborne system tasked with detecting, reporting and tracking enemy aerial movements within a certain area of operation.

Alpha Charlie -- Military alphabet used to represent ass chewing. Defines getting verbally reprimanded. Recommended by user Joe Trejo.

B - Bang-bang -- An Army term describing a pistol or rifle.

Big Voice -- Term used to describe the loudspeaker on a military base. The Big Voice warns of everything from incoming attacks to scheduled ordnance disposal.

Blue Falcon -- A euphemism for buddy which is slang for a backstabber. Recommended by user jp-chopper.

C - Chancre Mechanic -- Medical officer who checks service members for venereal diseases. Recommended by user jloman42.

Charlie Foxtrot -- Commonly used expression utilizing the military alphabet to stand for cluster.

D - Demilitarized Zone -- A specific area in which any type of military force -- including but not limited to personnel, hardware and infrastructure -- are banned.

Dope on a Rope -- Derogatory term used for air-assault soldiers.

Dust-off -- Specifically, a medical evacuation by helicopter.

E - Embed -- When a reporter stays with the military in order to conduct journalistic business. They typically are provided with security and basic necessities provided by the unit they are embedded with.

Expectant -- A casualty who is expected to pass die.

Eagle Keeper -- Maintenance crew chief of an F-15.

F - Fang -- A verb to describe being rebuked, called out or otherwise disparaged.

Fangs -- A Marine Corps term for one's teeth.

Fart Sack -- Refers to a sleeping bag or an airman's flight suit.

Five-Sided Puzzle Palace -- Slang for the Pentagon.

Football Bat -- An individual or way of doing things that is particularly odd.

Force Projection -- The ability of a nation-state to extend military force beyond their borders.

G - Grape -- A term with two meanings; one for the Air Force and one for the Navy. A Navy Grape is an individual who refuels aircraft. An Air Force Grape, on the other hand, refers to an easy assignment and can be used as a compliment when a service member makes something look easy.

Grid Squares -- A nonexistent item recruits typically are told to go find.

Gun -- Term for a mortar or artillery piece. Must never be used within the military to describe a pistol or rifle.

Gunner -- A service member who operates a crew-served weapon, such as a piece of artillery or ship's cannon. Recommended by user John Alfred.

H- Hangar Queen -- An aircraft that is used primarily for spare parts to repair other planes. Recommended by Steve Pinder.

Hat Up -- To change one's location. Refers to the need to wear a hat for the intended destination. Recommended by user JimBrown1946.

Hawk -- Term for cold weather. Commonly referred to as "the hawk."

Helo -- Short-hand term for a helicopter.

In conclusion, using military terms in teaching English is very important. When using military terms in English language cadets enhance their knowledge of specialized terminology by clarifying the meaning and practicing them in context.

References:

1. Назарова, С. В., and Р. Р. Атаев. "К вопросу о проблемах российского рынка труда." *Экономика и бизнес: теория и практика* 2-2 (2020): 62-66.
2. Атаева, Р. Р. "ТИПЫ СЛОВООБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ГНЕЗД В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.19 (2023): 313-319.
3. Атаева, Р. Р. "Поливершинные словообразовательные гнезда в русском языке. Дисс... д-ра философии (PhD) по филологическим наукам." *Автореф. дисс.... доктора философии (PhD).–Ташкент* (2020).
4. Атаева, Рануша Рашидовна. "СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОГО ГНЕЗДА." *Ответственный редактор* (2022): 34.
5. Nasirova, Saodat A. "Principles for translating vocabulary with background information." *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies* 2.07 (2022): 82-87.
6. Nasirova, Saodat. "Staff of officials of the Eastern Palace in ancient China." *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 12 (2022): 19-22.
7. Mirzakhmedova, Khulkar V., et al. "Use of Mobile Applications in Establishing Inclusive Education in Pedagogy." *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development* 11.12 (2023): e2376-e2376.
8. NASIROVA, SAODAT. "Human resource system of ancient China (chronological aspect)." *SHARQ MASH'ALI* 01 (2022): 31-32.
9. Abdullayevna, Nasirova Saodat. "上合组织国家的科学研究: 协同和一体化." *上合组织国家的科学研究: 协同和一体化* 87.0.
10. Nasirova, Saodat. "ГЕНДЕРНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В СИСТЕМЕ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА ЖЕНЩИН (НА ПРИМЕРЕ АНАЛИЗА ОПЫТА КИТАЯ В ВОПРОСЕ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТИ)." *Oriental Conferences*. Vol. 1. No. 1. ООО «SupportScience», 2023.
11. Rashidova, Munavvar Xaydarovna. "Instructional scaffolding to improve learning." *Innovative development in educational activities* 2.7 (2023): 135-140.
12. Rashidova, Munavvar Khaydarovna. "TECHNIQUES FOR IMPROVING CADETS' CONVERSATIONAL SKILLS." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 3.3 (2023): 637-640.
13. Рашидова, Мунаввар Хайдаровна. "Развитие коммуникативной компетенции в обучении курсантов устной речи." *Инновации в педагогике и психологии* 4.1 (2021).
14. Xaydarovna, Rashidova Munavvar. "Problems of teaching communicative English language at the Military Institute of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the ways of eliminating them." *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development* 5.3 (2020): 502-504.
15. Akhmedov, Doniyor A., et al. "Simulation of the effect of turning steering wheel intensity on the vehicle stability." *International journal of recent technology and engineering (IJRTE)* 9.2 (2020): 242-247.

16. Xaydarovna, Rashidova Munavvar, and Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. "Effective methods of teaching." *Materials of the republican* (2021): 23.
17. Xaydarovna, Rashidova Munavvar, and Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. "Review of the research on boburology abroad and in Uzbekistan." *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research* 2.09 (2020): 55-60.
18. Rashidova, M. X., and D. B. Namozova. "TEACHING TECHNICAL SUBJECTS THROUGH ENGLISH." *Ўзбекистонда миллий тадқиқотлар: даврий анжуманлар: 10-қисм*: 32.
19. Khaydarovna, Rashidova Munavvar. "Techniques for improving cadets' conversational skills." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Oriental renessans* 3.3 (2023): 637-640.
20. Hashimova, Sabohat Abdullaevna. "Peculiarities of Making Nouns Using Suffixes in Chinese (On the Example of Suffixes 家 "Jia" and 者 "Zhe")." *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding* 8.8 (2021): 367-370.
21. Khashimova, Sh K. "THE TEACHING OF LITERARY DISCIPLINES IS THE MAIN FACTOR AFFECTING EDUCATION." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 2.6 (2022): 313-316.
22. Mirzakhmedova, Khulkar V., et al. "Use of Mobile Applications in Establishing Inclusive Education in Pedagogy." *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development* 11.12 (2023): e2376-e2376.
23. Эгамбердиева, Г. М. "МЕТОДИЧЕСКАЯ РАЗРАБОТКА ПО РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ НА ТЕМУ «ВТОРОСТЕПЕННЫЕ ЧЛЕНЫ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯ»." *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ* 18.1 (2023): 41-44.
24. Kamilova, S. E., et al. "THE ORIGINALITY OF MODERN LITERATURE (On the example of the works of Ildar Abuzyarov, Timur Pulatovand, Zakhar Prilepin)." *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry* 12.9 (2021).
25. Madiyarovna, Egamberdieva Guzal, et al. "The Role of Folklore in the Development of Russian Literature (On the Example of the Stories of A. Platonov and S. Aflatuni)." *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry* 12.7 (2021).
26. Бульчѐва, Маргарита Фаритовна. "Актуальность изучения творчества эрнеста хемингуэя на сегодняшний день." *Academic research in educational sciences* 3.3 (2022): 298-304.
27. Бульчѐва, М. Ф. "РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ В АУДИТОРИИ УЧЕБНОЙ УСТНО-РЕЧЕВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ." *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi* 11.2 (2023): 87-91.
28. Бульчѐва, М. Ф. "К ВОПРОСУ О СПОСОБНОСТИ ОРГАНИЗОВЫВАТЬ МЫСЛЬ ПОСРЕДСТВОМ СЛОВА И ПРАКТИКЕ РАБОТЫ НАД КРАСНОРЕЧИЕМ."
29. Kenjabayevna, Darvishova Gulchehra. "USING VIDEOS IN EFL LESSONS." *Journal of new century innovations* 25.3 (2023): 91-93.
30. Дарвишова, Гулчехра Кенжабаевна. "THE ISSUES OF WOMEN AND SOCIETY IN THE NOVELS OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE." *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА* 4.4 (2021).
31. Kenjabayevna, Darvishova Gulchehra. "DESCRIPTION OF GENDER ISSUES IN THE NOVELS OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE." *TADQIQOTLAR* 26.1 (2023): 18-21.
32. Kenjabayevna, Darvishova Gulchehra. "ГРАММАТИК МАТЕРИАЛЛАРНИ ТАНЛАШНИНГ РОЛИ." *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования* 15.1 (2024): 150-154.

33. Дарвишова, Гулчехра Кенжабаевна. "ШАРЛОТТА БРОНТЕНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ИҚТИДОРИ." *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования* 14.4 (2024): 193-196.
34. Kenjabayevna, Darvishova Gulchehra. "'JANE EYRE" ROMANIDA TASVIRLANGAN AXLOQIY MUAMMO, GENDER VA TENGLIK MASALALARI." *Journal of new century innovations* 44.2 (2024): 86-90.
35. Darvishova, Gulchehra Kenjabayevna. "THE IMPORTANCE OF EQUALITY OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN THE WORKS OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 4.1 (2024): 345-352.
36. Shirinova, Nargiza. "USING GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY FOR STUDENTS OF ENGINEERING." *Irrigatsiya va Melioratsiya* 3 (2018): 89-92.
37. Shirinova, N. D. "Shirinova ND GRADUAL MORPHOLOGICAL DEMARCATION OF SUBSTANTIVE AND ATTRIBUTIVE MEANINGS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES." (2022).
38. Shirinova, N. D. "Personal and Professional Upbringing of Learners by Specific Approach to the learning English." *Irrigatsiya va Melioratsiya* 2 (2017): 66-69.
39. Ширинова, Нилуфар Джаббаровна, and Мухайё Хасановна Давлатова. "МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ СПОСОБ РАЗГРАНИЧЕНИЯ ЗНАЧЕНИЙ ПРЕДМЕТНОСТИ И КАЧЕСТВЕННОСТИ В СИСТЕМЕ ЯЗЫКА." *Muassis: Buxoro davlat universiteti TAHRIRIYAT: Muharrirlar: MQ Abuzalova MA Bokareva NN Voxidova* 40.
40. Shirinova, N., and Abdullaeva N. Lets Learn English. "for Agriculture. Study-book for the students of agriculture." (2016).
41. Shirinova, N., and N. Abdullayeva. "English for You. Study-book for the intermediate students of irrigation and melioration." (2014).
42. Менглиева, Сунбула. "Increasing the professional competence of cadets through the method of projects." *Общество и инновации* 3.10/S (2022): 296-300.
43. Mengliyeva, S. S. "SOHAVIY TERMINLARNING LISONIY XUSUSIYATLARI." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.19 (2023): 293-300.
44. Менглиева, С. С. "Коммуникативные помехи в речи." *БАШКОРТОСТАН РЕСПУБЛИКАҲИНДА ҺӘМ РӘСӘЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИЯҲЫНЫҢ БАШКА ТӨБӘКТӘРЕНДӘ БАШКОРТ ТЕЛЕН УҚЫТЫУЗЫҢ ХӘЗЕРГЕ ПРОБЛЕМАЛАРЫ.* 2020.
45. Namozova, Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. "The problems of phonetic interference in speech of cadets." *Science and Education* 3.7 (2022): 192-196.
46. Berdimurotovna, Namozova Dilnoza. "The role and place of English in international communication." *Chief Editor* (2020).
47. Namozova, Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. "DEVELOPMENT OF PHONETIC COMPETENCE IN CONDITIONS OF ARTIFICIAL MULTILINGUALISM." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 3.4 (2023): 356-360.